

Articles series, part 4: Tolerances in implant dentistry. Effect of the shouldered abutment design from Straumann on the implant-abutment connection performance.

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Abstract

Many variations in the implant designs are not good as they marketing for them. In many times the implant accessories designs are base on imaginations rather than solid mechanical concepts. Shouldered abutment designs need special attention to investigate its performance. This design is highly compromising the implant abutment connection as it will lead to more disturbed stresses distributions.

Keywords: Straumann, TLX implant, Titanium corrosion, Implant-Abutment connection

Introduction

Straumann had an iconic design of the tissue level implant that had been gaining a wide acceptance and had been adopted by many other companies (1). This design was invented to evade the crestal bone loss (2). This design had many biomechanical aspects to be discussed, but in this paper we want to highlight the first issue that need to be address which the effect of manufacturing tolerances (3).

Figure 1 Straumann iconic connection is apparent

As we say earlier, we regard this variation in the design is an escape from the ominous titanium release near the bone and placing higher in the tissue level. This escaping and remedy solution without addressing the main issue. (4)

Figure 2 The base of the titanium base is evident. This is the design used by Straumann for prosthetic rehabilitation

Figure 3 the conversion of good connection to poor variation is evident

Some abutment of the Straumann is highly contraindicated. By making shouldered design we will reintroduce the flat-on-flat surface in another form (5)

Figure 4 In the next paper we will present a new paper about tolerances in the multiunit abutment. They incorporate this design in many prosthetic solutions

In our previous papers, we had demonstrated clearly the effect of the tolerances on the design and performance where we cannot prevent tolerances from occurring, but just obviate its essentially inherited presence.

Methods

The used model in the previous papers had been changed to make this simulation. The models had been modeled and test inside of the SolidWorks 2022 (Dassault Systems, USA) environment

Figure 5 We had mimicked the design of Straumann to represent the core of the idea. Blue surface is intended to have the contact between the abutment and the implant

This model had no rational cause to manufacture it. The machining at 2 sides at inner and outer would produce the worst tolerances as it involves multiple change in the position of the cutting tools and retrieval and engagement in the cutting tools (6)

Figure 6 The implant abutment connection is apparent

We had supposed the tolerance is to be 10 microns which could be considered as a tight value (7). As we might had tolerances in opposite direction in the implant and abutment, we had supposed the gap to be 20 microns.

Figure 7 The gap is at the outer region of 20 microns

Figure 8 Another variation is the gap at the inner side

The boundaries condition involves 3 elements which had been simplified in Figure 9

- The preload, which had been supposed as a virtual bolt that connect the abutment to the implant
- Fixed base
- Horizontal force application

Figure 9 The lower face is fixed and the violet arrows indicate the force application area. The blue virtual bolt represents the connecting screw

Results and discussions

First evaluation criteria is the situation of the virtual connecting screw. We had chosen the axial force to get an insight about the tension that the connecting screw will be exposed to. The evaluation of the connecting screw is of paramount importance

Shear Force (N)	19.484	Counterbore with Nut-1
Axial Force (N)	347.69	Counterbore with Nut-1
Bending moment (N.m)	0.015572	Counterbore with Nut-1
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-1

Figure 10 This is for the perfect contact 2 regions

Type	Resultant	Connector
Shear Force (N)	17.049	Counterbore with Nut-
Axial Force (N)	411.86	Counterbore with Nut-
Bending moment (N.m)	0.030796	Counterbore with Nut-
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-

Figure 11 This is for the gap at the outer region

Type	Resultant	Connector
Shear Force (N)	60.961	Counterbore with Nut-1
Axial Force (N)	375.31	Counterbore with Nut-1
Bending moment (N.m)	0.027764	Counterbore with Nut-1
Torque (N.m)	0	Counterbore with Nut-1

Figure 12 This is for the gap at the inner surface

Figure 13 Von Mises stress of the both perfect region

Figure 14 Displacement of the both perfect contact region

Figure 15 In all other models the outer rim had failed to show any benefit, nut just increase the corrosion at the other side away from the force application side due to changed contact pressure pattern

Figure 16 Both are in perfect condition

Previous models are perfect in out and inner surfaces. Next models are perfect in the inner surface only and for the outer surface we had gap of 20 microns

Figure 17 The gap is present at the outer surface only

Figure 18 Displacement of the model with gap at the outer surface only

Figure 19 Contact pressure pattern should be evaluated carefully. This is the model with outer surface gap

Figure 20 Other representation of the contact pressure with the model with outer surface gap

All the previous model are with outer surfaces gap and the inner surfaces are perfectly contacted. Next models are with gap at the inner surfaces.

Figure 21 Von Mises stress of the model with gap at the inner surfaces

Figure 22 Displacement of the model with the gap at the inner surfaces

Figure 23 Contact pressure with the gap at the inner surfaces

Figure 24 Contact pressure representation with the gap at the inner surfaces

We should always emphasize upon the fact that these represent the ultimate status after loading and the development of the deformation should be always sought in both numerical and physical models. In the current models we had demonstrated clearly the effect of the tolerances on the performance of the implant abutment connection. The design had failed to show a beneficial benefit and the outer rim is of no real value. It will produce significant corrosion and had no addition of any sort on the strengthening of the abutment implant connection. The gap opening at the side of the force application is apparent. This design should be reviewed according to the machining tolerances as well as the mechanical criteria associated with it. The tolerances produced by the implant company is much less than those produced by the local dental laboratories. The performance of the implant model with perfect fit is close to the performance that had been resulted from the model with outer region gap. The worst results were observed with the implant with gap at the inner region. Although we hadn't done it, implant abutment ratio should be evaluated which is one of the most important criteria. As with all of any issue of the tolerances CMM machines should be implemented to evaluate this

issue of tolerances. Nevertheless, this design is regarded as futile design from the point of view of the main author as the deeper connection is not necessary to be considered.

The criteria in our paper about cone importance should be recruited here

This is an introductory paper about the design of Straumann iconic connection. This connection had been introduced to mitigate the effect of bone loss crestal

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in may researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial

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